

Effect of alcohol and narcotic drug intake among undergraduates of Kwara State University Malete, Nigeria

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(02), 2270–2297

Publication history: Received on 17 July 2024; revised on 24 August 2024; accepted on 26 August 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.2.2476>

Abstract

Background: Alcohol and narcotic drug use have a long history together. Students in postsecondary institutions frequently use alcohol along with other substances like cannabis, nicotine, tramadol, codeine, and other amphetamines. These substances have detrimental effects on both the user and society at large, so it is absolutely essential to discover what is causing the continued use of these substances.

Aim: To determine the effect of alcohol and narcotic intake among undergraduates of Kwara state university, Malete, Nigeria

Method: This study is a descriptive cross-sectional study, designed to assess the effect of alcohol and narcotic intake among undergraduates in Kwara State University, malete using a qualitative method of data collection. The questionnaire was administered to determine the sample size using a simple random technique to get the desired sample size from the study population

Result: Relationship between the social demographic response of the participants regarding their knowledge, effects of narcotic drugs and alcohol on the body and types of narcotic commonly used by undergraduates and factors motivating the use of narcotic drugs alcohol. Using Chi-Square set with the level of significance $p < 0.05$ alongside with degree of freedom.

Considering the relationship between the gender of the respondents towards their knowledge about drugs and narcotics among the undergraduates, 40(20%) were female respondents, while 160(80%) of them were male respondents. P. value = $0.000 < 0.05$, which shows that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

Considering the relationship between the age of the respondents and the knowledge, 17-18 years were 40 (20%), 19-20years were 80(40%) while 21 and above were 80(40%) with P-value = $0.00 < 0.05$ indicating that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

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Also, regarding the relationship between religion and their knowledge about knowledge, 100(50%) of the respondents were Muslims, 60(40%) were Christians, while 20(10%) were traditional. P-value = 0.00 < 0.05 meaning that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

Conclusion: On our campus, there is an urgent need for preventive public health measures. It is recommended to launch more awareness efforts about the harmful effects of alcohol and narcotic medications. The use of alcohol and other drugs presents a serious threat to our future generations. Every single person ought to be discouraged by it.

Keywords: Alcohol; Narcotic Drugs; Alcohol; Effect; Undergraduate

1. Introduction

Drinking alcohol along with consuming narcotic substances has been discovered to be a significant risk factor for disease, disability, and death in many developing nations, including Nigeria.¹ Alcohol intake, especially heavy drinking, has a negative impact on the immune system, which is one way that it raises the risk for chronic diseases.^{2,3}

In support of this claim,⁴ pointed out that alcohol has been around for a very long time and is thought to be the first chemical mood enhancer ever discovered. In traditional African religion, alcohol plays a significant role in the deity worship.

The negative consequences of undergraduates drinking include a range of physical problems, academic problems, social problems, criminal convictions, and financial problems. Peer group influence, environment, ineffective parenting/guardian, experimentation, poor school performance, access to drugs are reported to be the primary cause for alcohol and narcotic drugs usage among undergraduates of Kwara State University. High rates of alcohol use are also associated with risky sexual behaviour among university students. Many reasons had been established for alcohol usage. Muslims have a significantly lower alcohol consumption rate than people of other religions.⁵ Adekeye suggests that young people who witness or are exposed to alcohol- and tobacco-consuming adults may wish to try it out for themselves.⁶

Humans have been looking for materials that would both operate on the nervous system to create pleasure feelings and sustain and protect them since the dawn of time. Because they induce inner peace and contentment, relax the muscles, and heighten perception, drugs are thought to be pleasurable.⁷

Narcotic drugs are referred to as substances that alter behavior, mood, brain function, perception, and general bodily functioning.⁸ Drugs are additionally believed to be a material whose chemical actions have the potential to alter how the body functions.⁹ Cultural norms, attitudes towards drug use, and values appear to have an impact on the frequency of drug addictions in a given community. These factors vary widely between cultures and geographical places.¹⁰ If help is not given right away, this could be a symptom of illicit substance usage, which could lead to misuse of drugs as well as dependency.⁶

A person's likelihood of developing a drug addiction or misuse condition can be increased by a variety of biological, psychological, and social factors that are together referred to as risk factors. Substance addiction disorders seem to run more prevalent in some families than what might be explained by a home setting that is addictive. According to Foo, parental substance abuse habits have the greatest impact on a child's substance abuse.¹¹

It is a given that most university campuses struggle to limit and regulate the amount of alcohol that their students consume. This is because the age at which students first enroll in these institutions is a period of experimentation, during which time teenagers have the opportunity to test the boundaries that have already been established by their parents, guardians, and schools.

Adekeye claims that drug experimentation occurs among Nigerian college students who are unaware of the proper substances to take, when it is they should use them⁶, or which way to take them. Nowadays, risky alcohol consumption among Nigerian university students has become a major public health issue.¹²

The persistence of high levels of alcohol and narcotic drugs intake in a large proportion of Kwara State University undergraduates stresses the need for effective preventive and treatment interventions for both sexes. In addition to a research conducted in Nigeria by Obot and Ibanga,¹³ over 97,000 university students had experienced alcohol-related sexual assault or abuse, and a number of others said they were too drunk to remember whether or not they gave their consent to have sex.¹⁴ The use and misuse of alcohol and narcotic substances has an impact on students' health in

schools since, among other social and health issues, they are a major source of increased crime and a high rate of unintentional injury. In an urban region of Central Nigeria, 292 male teenagers, aged 11 to 20, who were not enrolled in school were the subjects of a study conducted by Ayenigboro and Adegboro.¹⁵ The study's findings revealed that 38.7% of the sample, or over 3% of the total, had consumed alcohol at least once in their lifetime.

2. Material and Methods

This study is a descriptive cross-sectional study, designed to assess the effect of alcohol and narcotic drug intake among undergraduates in Kwara state university, malete, Nigeria using a qualitative method of data collection. The questionnaire was administered to determine the sample size. The inclusion criteria for the selection of study subjects are all undergraduates of Kwara state university, malete who are willing to participate in the exercise while exclusion criteria for selection of study subjects are all undergraduates within Kwara state university, malete who are not willing to participate in the exercise.

Our minimum sample size had a confidence Interval of 95% and normal deviate of 1.96 as determined using the Fisher's formula for sample size determination where the population is greater than 10,000 stated below:¹⁶

A self-administered questionnaire was used for this study. The questionnaire contained close-ended questions; it was used to collect information on the effect of alcohol and narcotic drugs intake among undergraduates in Kwara state university, malete.

The data collection instrument was given to the researcher's supervisor for their expert advice on the standard and content validity of the instrument of data collection for this study, and adjustment was made based on the correction made by the supervisor.

In order to detect inconsistencies and test its validity and reliability as a research instrument, the questionnaires (10% of the sample) was pre-tested among undergraduates of Kwara State Polytechnic. This is intending to determine its accuracy and suitability as a research instrument for the study and to ascertain any difficulty the researcher may come across when carrying out the main study. The pre-tested questionnaires were analyzed and necessary modifications were made before its eventual use for data collection just as it was done in the main study.

A self-administered questionnaire was used for this study. Semi-structured questionnaires and close-ended interview questions were used to collect data for this study. The questionnaire was divided into various sections.

The data collected from the respondents were entered, organized and stored in a tabular form in a spreadsheet. This will be achieved by using the Microsoft excel

The questionnaire was collected and thoroughly checked for completeness and consistency. The data collected from the field was then organized and analyzed. The analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20, descriptive statistics package, using Simple Cross Tabulation Analysis. The incomplete and inaccurate questionnaire was not used in the analysis. The results were interpreted with the aid of descriptive statistics such as bar charts, frequencies and percentages etc.

Consent was gotten from the Students Affairs Office before undertaking the exercise. Assurance of the anonymity and confidentiality of the data from the respondents was given to them and also maintained for the duration and purpose of the study.

3. Results and Data Analysis

Out of 218 questionnaires administered among undergraduates of Kwara state university, malete, Nigeria it was only 200 were returned, the remaining 18 questionnaires were not responded to. Therefore; the result was only for 200 responses.

Data analysis was performed by a simple cross-tabulation analysis to test variables such as social-demographic characteristics, knowledge about alcohol and narcotic drugs, effects of narcotic drug and alcohol on the body, type of narcotic drugs commonly used by undergraduates and factors that motivate the use of narcotic drug and alcohol.

Answers to open-ended questions were transcribed by the researcher, which was then analysed by the thematic method of analysis. Inferences were made from the data collected through open-ended questions to support and complement the data from closed-ended questions.

The following paragraphs present the analysis of data collected from the two hundred (200) respondents from undergraduate students of Kwara state university, Malete, Kwara State. The analysis includes the social-demographic characteristics, knowledge about alcohol and narcotic drugs, effects of narcotic drugs and alcohol on the body, type of narcotic drugs commonly used by undergraduates and factors that motivate the use of narcotic drugs and alcohol.

3.1. Socio-Demographic Data

The table below showing respondents by sex distribution: Female (40 (20.0%)); and Male (160 (80%)). The results of the survey show that the effect of alcoholic and narcotic drugs intake has no gender limit and it affects most gender. This implies that this study is not gender bias.

3.2. Gender of respondents

Table 1 Distribution of respondents by sex

	Frequency	%	Valid %
MALE	160	80.0	80.0
FEMALE	40	20.0	20.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation

Figure 1 Bar chart showing the distribution of respondents by sex

3.2.1. Age of Respondents

Table 2 Distribution of respondents by age

	Frequency	Percentage
Valid17-18	40	20.0
19-20	80	40.0
21 and above	80	40.0
Total	200	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation

The table below shows respondents age distribution as follows: 17-18years (40 (20.0%)); 19-20years (80 (40%)); and, 21years and above (80(40.0%)). The results of the survey that the effect of alcoholic and narcotic drug intake has no age limit but is more prevalent among people age 19 to 20 and age 21 above. This is because they are not new in the academic system, unlike those that are just coming into the system.

Figure 2 Bar chart showing respondents age distribution

3.2.2. Religion of Respondents

Table 3 Distribution of respondents by religion

	Frequency	Percentage	Valid Percentage
Valid Islam	100	50.0	50.0
Christianity	80	40.0	40.0
Traditional	20	10.0	10.0
Total	200	100.0	100.0

Source: Researcher's Computation

The data obtained revealed that the majority of the respondents were Muslim 100(50%), those are Christian consist of 80(40%), while the remaining are 20(10%). The data also revealed that the effect of alcoholic and narcotic drug intake among undergraduates was common among Muslims, Compared to Christians and those that chose to be practising traditional religion. This is not to say that effect does not occur among Christian and traditionalists as the data collected showed that 80(40%) of respondents from Christian and 20(10%) from traditionalists were shown to have to be partly affected in the area of study.

Figure 3 Bar chart showing the distribution of respondents by religion

3.3. Knowledge about Alcohol and Narcotic Drugs

Figure 4 Bar chart showing the response of respondents about knowledge of alcohol

According to the responses provided by the participants, about 32.8 % of them do not take alcohol at all, while about 67.2 % of Kwara state university malete, Nigeria still taking alcohol, although the level and rate of consumption are differs.

This result disagrees with,¹⁷ whose study revealed that the predominance of current alcohol use among a sample of Nigerian optional school students was 30.6% and that 38.1% of current consumers had likewise been drunk in the previous 30 days, with 17.2% being drunk most of the time. Although, this study agrees with Adelekan,¹⁸ whose investigation among 292 out-of-school male youths in an urban territory of Central Nigeria (aged 11 to 20 years) found that more than 33% (38.7%) of the sample had taken alcohol at any rate once in their lives.

Figure 5 Bar chart showing the result of respondents on the knowledge of narcotic drug

Base on the response provided by the respondents 80% does not take narcotics drug, while 20% of Kwara state university malete Nigeria still taking narcotic drugs.

Figure 6 Bar chart showing the knowledge of the respondent about the drug that causes addiction

According to the response provided by the respondents, 73% says tramadol is the most that cause addiction, while 23% says crack, 4% goes for rephnol.

Figure 7 Bar chart showing results of respondents about forms of narcotic drug available

According to the result of responses provided by the respondents 46% says cigarette is mostly available and accessible, while 33% says tablet 12% goes for powder and 9% for rephnol.

3.4. Factors that motivate the intake of Narcotic Drug and Alcohol Joy seeking

Figure 8 Bar chart showing the response of respondents on the factor that motivate the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

According to the responses provided by the participants, 120(60%) of them saw it as least important for joy seeking, 60(30%) saw it as important for joy seeking, while 20(10%) saw it as most important, that without taking it they cannot be as happy as desired.

3.4.1. Psychological Disorder

According to the responses provided by the participants, 140(70%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important in the case of psychological disorder, while 60(30%) of them saw it as important.

Figure 9 Bar chart showing the response of respondents about psychological disorder

3.4.2. Lack of knowledge about complications of drugs/ alcohol

Figure 10 Bar chart showing the result of response about the lack of knowledge about complications of alcohol and narcotic drug

According to the responses provided by the participants, 100(50%) were of least important, 80(40%) were of the view that it is important and 20(10%) thought that it is most important, that lack of knowledge about computerlocation of drug and alcohol serves as a factor or motivating the intake of drug and alcohol.

3.4.3. Low self-esteem

According to the responses provided by the participants, 60(30%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important, 40(20%) were of the view that it is important and 100(50%) believed that it is most important, that low esteem serves as a factor motivating the intake of drug and alcohol.

Figure 11 Bar chart showing the response of respondents about low self-esteem

3.4.4. To Eliminate Shyness

As regards the responses of the participants provided, 180(80%) of the total responses thought that it is least important that the use of drugs and alcohol serves as a motivating factor to eliminate shyness, while 40(20%) supported that it serves as an important factor.

Figure 12 Bar chart showing the response of the respondents about shyness as the factor that motivate the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.5. Boredom

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 80 (40%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking drugs and narcotics could be as a result of being bored, 80(40%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 13 Bar chart showing the result of the response from the respondents about boredom as the factor that motivate the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.5.1. Having Strict Parents

Figure 14 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about having strict parents as a factor that motivate the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 100 (50%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result having strict parents, 20(10%) thought that it is important, while 80(40%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

3.5.2. Access to Narcotic Drugs/ Alcohol

Figure 15 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents about access to narcotic drug and alcohol

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 140(70%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and alcohol could be as a result having access to both the drug and alcohol, 40(20%) thought that it is important, while 20(10%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

3.6. Low cost of Alcohol and Narcotic

Figure 16 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents about low cost

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 120(60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of cheapness in the price of both drug and alcohol, 60(30%) thought that it is important, while 20(10%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

3.7. Having free time

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 60(30%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result being less busy, 80(40%) thought that it is important, while 60(30%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 17 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents about having free time

3.8. Presence of an Addicted person in the residence

Figure 18 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about the presence of an addicted person in the residential as a factor that motivate the intake of alcohol and narcotic

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result presence of an addicted person in the residence, 40(20%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

3.8.1. Peer Pressure

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of peer pressure and influence, 40(20%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 19 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about peer pressure as the factor that motivates intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.8.2. Academic Stress

Figure 20 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about academic stress as a factor that motivates the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

According to the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 140 (70%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of academic stress, while 60(30%) thought that it is an important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

3.8.3. Curiosity for experimentation

Base on the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 100 (50%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of curiosity for experimentation, 60(30%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 21 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents about curiosity for experimentation

3.9. To get High or Intoxication

According to the responses of the participants, 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of narcotic drug and alcohol could be as a result of being high or get intoxicated, 40(20%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 22 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about to get intoxicated or high as the factor that motivates intake of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.9.1. Sleep

According to the responses of the participants, 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drug and narcotic could be as a result sleepless situation experienced to get slept, 40(20%) thought that it is important, while 40(20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 23 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about sleep as a factor that motivates the intake

3.9.2. For pleasure

According to the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 160 (80%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of pleasure derivation, while 40(20%) thought that it is an important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Figure 24 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents concerning pleasure

3.10. To concentrate

Figure 25 Bar chart showing the result of the response from respondents about 'to concentrate' as a factor that motivates the intake

According to the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 160 (80%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of being fully devoted and get concentrated, while 40(20%) thought that it is an important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

I drink because when I stop, I feel bad

Figure 26 Bar chart showing the result of responses from respondents

According to the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and narcotics could be as a result of depression, while 80(40%) thought that it is an important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

In summary, based on the findings of this study, it was observed that factors that motivate the use of narcotic drugs and alcohol among undergraduates are: lack of knowledge about complications of drug/alcohol, low self-esteem, boredom, having strict parents, having free time, peer pressure and curiosity for experimentation.

3.11. Effects of Intake of Alcohol and Narcotic Drugs

3.11.1. Improved memory and Learning Ability

According to the responses provided by the participants, 180(90%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could boost memory and improve learning ability, while 20(10%) agreed that it serves as an avenue to boost and improve both memory and ability to learn

Figure 27 Bar chart showing the result of respondents on the effect of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.12. Depression

Base on the responses provided by the participants, 40(20%) of the total respondents disagreed that taking alcohol and the narcotic drug could cause depression to live of the person involved, while 160(80%) agreed that it could cause depression especially when one eventually get addicted to it.

Figure 28 Bar chart showing the result of respondents

3.13. Increase in self-confidence

According to the responses provided by the participants, 160(80%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could increase self-confidence and drive away cowardice, while 40(20%) agreed that it serves as an avenue to increase self-confidence.

Figure 29 Bar chart showing the result of respondents

3.14. Better acceptability by friends

According to the responses provided by the participants, 180(90%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could result in better acceptability by friends, while 20(10%) agreed that it serves as an avenue of better acceptability by friends

Figure 30 Bar chart showing the results of the respondents

3.15. Better Academic Performance

Figure 31 Bar chart showing the result of respondents

According to the responses provided by the participants, 180(90%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could result in better academic performance, while 20(10%) agreed that it serves as an avenue of better academic performance.

3.16. Increase Sexual Performance

Figure 32 Bar chart showing the result of the respondents

According to the responses provided by the participants, 120(60%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could increase sexual performance, while 80(40%) agreed that it serves as an avenue to increase sexual performance.

3.17. Reduced Sexual Performance

According to the responses provided by the participants, 80(40%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could reduce sexual performance, while 120(60%) agreed that it serves as an avenue to reduce sexual performance.

Figure 33 Bar chart showing the result of the respondents

3.18. Better Mental Health

Figure 34 Bar chart showing the result of respondents

According to the responses provided by the participants, 160(80%) of the total respondents disagreed that intake of alcohol and the narcotic drug could bring about better mental health, while 40(20%) agreed that it serves as a channel to achieve mental health.

3.18.1. Liver or Kidney Damage/ Failure

Base on the responses provided by the participants, 20(10%) disagreed the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug causes kidney damage and failure, 40(20%) were indifferent, while 140(70%) agreed that it causes kidney damage and failure.

Figure 35 Bar chart showing the result of respondents about liver or kidney failure is as a result of the effect of alcohol and narcotic drug

3.19. Mental Illness

Figure 36 Bar chart showing the result of the respondents about mental illness also is an effect of alcohol and narcotic drug

Base on the responses provided by the participants, 20(10%) disagreed the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug causes mental illness, 40(20%) were indifferent, while 140(70%) agreed that it causes mental illness.

3.20. Death

Base on the responses provided by the participants, 20(10%) disagreed the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug causes the death of the person involved, 20(10%) were indifferent, while 160(80%) agreed that it causes the death of the person involved.

In summary, based on the findings of this study, it was observed that depression, reduction in sexual performance, liver or kidney damage/ failure, mental illness and death are the effects of a narcotic drug and alcoholic on the body, while others are considered not to be the effects on the body.

Figure 37 Bar chart showing the result of respondents about as an effect of narcotic drug and alcohol

3.21. Types of Drug Commonly Used by Undergraduates

Figure 38 Bar chart showing the result of respondents concerning the type of drugs commonly used by undergraduates

According to the result of responses provided by the respondents 70% (140) says codeine is the most commonly used among undergraduates, while 20% (40) says tramadol, 10% (20) rephnol.

Table 4 Relationship between the social demographic response of the participants regarding their knowledge about alcohol and narcotic drugs

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Chi-Square	DF
Gender				
Female	40	20.0	72.00	1
Male	160	80.0		
Total	200	100		
AGE				
17-18	40	20.0	16.00	2
19-20	80	40.0		
21 and above	80	40.0		
Total	200	100		
Religion				
Islam	100	50.0	52.00	2
Christianity	60	40.0		
Traditional	20	10.0		
Total	200	100		

Above table 4 shows the relationship between the social demographic response of the participants regarding their knowledge about alcohol and narcotic drugs, effects of narcotic drugs and alcohol on the body and types of narcotic drugs commonly used by undergraduates and factors motivating the use of narcotic drugs and alcohol. Using Chi-Square set with the level of significance $p < 0.05$ alongside with degree of freedom.

Regarding the relationship between the gender of the respondents towards their knowledge about alcohol and narcotic drugs among the undergraduates, 40(20%) were female respondents, while 160(80%) of them were male respondents. P. value = $0.000 < 0.05$, which shows that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

Regarding the relationship between the age of the respondents and the knowledge of narcotics and alcohol among undergraduates, 17-18 years were 40(20%), 19-20years were 80(40%) while 21 and above were 80(40%) with a P value = $0.00 < 0.05$ indicating that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

Also, regarding the relationship between religion and their knowledge about knowledge of narcotic drugs and alcohol among undergraduates, 100(50%) of the respondents were Muslims, 60(40%) were Christians, while 20(10%) were Traditional. P-value = $0.00 < 0.05$ meaning that it is significant, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis.

4. Discussion

These findings provide evidence that increased alcohol and narcotic drugs consumption exists among undergraduates of Kwara State University. Most students consume alcohol and narcotic drugs regularly and they see them as an integral part of their higher-education life. According to the responses provided by the participants, 100(50%) were of least important that lack of knowledge about complications of drugs and alcohol serves as contributing factor to the consumption of drugs and alcohol, 80(40%) were of the view that it is important and 20(10%) thought that it is most important.

According to the responses provided by the participants, about 32.8 % of them do not take alcohol at all, while about 67.2 % of Kwara state university malete, Nigeria still taking alcohol, although the level and rate of consumption are differs.

This finding conflicts with the findings of Alex-Hart BA, Opara PI and Okagua J,¹⁷ whose research found that among a sample of Nigerian optional school students, 30.6% of current users reported currently using alcohol, and 38.1% of current users reported having consumed alcohol in the thirty days preceding the current study, with 17.2% reporting being drunk almost all the time at that time. This study, however, concurs with Adelekan ML¹⁸ whose study of 292 male

teenagers (ages 11 to 20) who were not enrolled in school in an urban area of Central Nigeria revealed that over 33% (38.7%) of the sample had consumed alcohol at least once in their life.

The respondents' age distribution was as follows: 17-18 years 40 (20.0%); 19-20years (80 (40%); and, 21years and above 80 (40.0%). This demonstrates that the effect of alcoholic and narcotic drug intake has no age limit but is more prevalent among people age 19 to 20 and age 21 above. This is because they are not new in the academic system, unlike those that are just coming into the system.

The data obtained revealed that half of the respondents were Muslim 100 (50%), 80 (40%) were Christians, while the remaining 20 (10%) are Traditionalists. The data also shows that the effect of alcoholic and narcotic drug intake among undergraduates was common among Muslims, compared to Christians and those that chose to be practising Traditional religion. This does not mean that the effect does not common among Christians and Traditionalists also as the data collected showed that 80 (40%) of respondents from Christian and 20 (10%) from traditionalists were shown to have to be partly affected in the area of study.

Base on the results obtained, more than half of the respondents 120 (60%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drugs and alcohol could be as a result of peer pressure influence, 40 (20%) thought that it is important, while 40 (20%) were of the view that it is a most important contributing factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

According to the results presented with regards to the responses of the participants, 100 (50%) of the total respondents were of the view that it is least important that taking of drug and narcotic drugs could be as a result of curiosity for experimentation, 60 (30%) thought that it is important, while 40 (20%) were of the view that it is the most important motivating factor for the use of drug and alcohol.

Base on the responses provided by the participants, 20 (10%) disagreed the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug causes kidney damage and failure, 40 (20%) were indifferent, while more than half 140 (70%) agreed that it causes kidney damage and failure.

According to the result of the responses provided by the participants, 20 (10%) disagreed the intake of alcohol and narcotic drug causes mental illness, 40 (20%) were indifferent, while more than half 140 (70%) agreed that it causes mental illness.

5. Conclusion

All of the variables are statistically significant to the youth alcoholic usage, and the results collectively show that peer influence, family background, emotion, easily accessibility, boredom, and having free time are predictors of alcohol and narcotic drug usage among undergraduates. However, it is observed that having free time, peer influence, emotion, and boredom are the best predictors, while family background remains the least.

The results also concluded that undergraduates of Kwara state university malete, consume alcohol and narcotic drugs which shows that male undergraduates were consuming alcohol and narcotic drugs than female undergraduates.

5.1. Recommendation

Whatever the data may be in favour of youth alcohol consumption, it always signals danger, and the negative effects will much outweigh the benefits. Therefore, every effort needs to be taken to raise awareness among young people in order to lower the drinking age as well as the quantity and dosage of alcohol and other substances used. The government can enact laws prohibiting underage alcohol consumption until they reach legal drinking age. This will delay the inception of alcohol consumption, potentially lowering the risk of alcohol-related harm. Since many university campuses or areas around them sell alcoholic drinks in a variety of forms and varieties as well as other stimulants and depression-inducing substances, more youth directed awareness campaigns about the detrimental consequences of alcohol and substance use is advocated.

After the results of this study have been discussed and a conclusion drawn, it is necessary to offer some recommendations for thought: When helping clients who are alcoholics, social workers, counsellors, and public health advocates should consider these factors. Adolescents who consume alcohol can be reformed by positive peer pressure. Furthermore, as young people are easily influenced to adopt negative behaviours, parents are urged to set a positive example for their offspring.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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